

COORDINATED MULTIAGENT NEURAL NETWORK ARCHITECTURE FOR REAL-TIME DECISION MAKING IN AN INTELLIGENT NETWORKED ENVIRONMENT

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17529812>

Abstract: Urban traffic congestion poses a persistent challenge in rapidly developing regions such as Port Harcourt, Nigeria. Traditional methods often lack adaptability to dynamic urban road networks. In this paper, a coordinated multi-agent deep reinforcement learning (MADRL) system that leverages graph neural networks (GNNs) for optimizing traffic flow is presented. The methodology involves building a custom environment that mirrors the Road topology of Port Harcourt and deploying agents to minimize congestion across hotspots. These agents are trained using DQNs enhanced with graph layers to capture spatial dependencies between junctions. A dense variational Bayesian layer is used to improve Q-value approximation generalization. The custom environment replaces traditional OpenAI Gym simulations, allowing for direct dataset-based learning. The empirical results demonstrate the model's robustness, achieving steady learning with low entropy (0.03) and high reward stability across episodes, resulting in steady reward growth.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence; reinforcement learning; traffic congestion

Introduction

AI has evolved into a critical enabler of technological progress, particularly in urban planning and transportation. In 2025, the National Information Technology Development Agency (NITDA) emphasized the strategic importance of AI in the Nigerian context during a keynote on "Harnessing AI for Strategic Leadership." Complementing this, a recent review, *Artificial Intelligence in Nigeria: A Catalyst for Economic Growth, Innovation, and Technological Advancement (2025)*, estimated that Nigeria had over 164 million Internet users and 219 million mobile subscribers as of Q1 2024. This infrastructure provides fertile ground for the deployment of AI-based solutions to public challenges. Rebecca et al. (2024) examined the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into Nigeria's educational sector, identifying key issues such as algorithmic complexity and low levels of trust. Robinson (2018) earlier highlighted global concerns, including cultural barriers and software malfunctions that hinder the widespread adoption of AI in developing nations.

Transportation is one of the most promising sectors for AI applications. Skrabacz et al. (2024) explored AI-powered ITS to reduce road fatalities. Zhang et al. (2022) proposed a centralized training and decentralized execution paradigm using MADRL to minimize utility costs. Earlier, Ong et al. (2015) developed a distributed

traffic control model inspired by the parallelism research of MIT, offering a scalable alternative to conventional approaches.

Study Area

Itaa, Ugwoha and Yorkor (2023) focus on a section of the East-West Road in Port Harcourt that runs from Choba to the Oil Mill, as shown in Figure 1. Taa, Ugwoha, and Yorkor (2023) stated that Port Harcourt is located roughly 1,811.6 km² between latitudes 4°45'N and 4°55'N and longitudes 6°55'E and 7°05'E. Crucial intersections that act as the main entry points into the city are Choba, Rumuokoro, Elioazu, and Eleme. Eleme Junction, which links Port Harcourt to nearby states via the East-West Road and is close to the crowded Oil Mill Market, is prone to heavy traffic.

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Figure 1: Study area map

Methodology

Multi-Agent Deep Reinforcement Learning

The method adopts Jung et al.'s (2021) multi-agent deep reinforcement learning framework, originally used for UAV scheduling. The MADRL system comprises multiple agents interacting with an environment to collaboratively learn optimal policies. Deep Q-Networks (DQN) is the learning foundation, where agents compute Q-values representing the expected return of taking an action in a specific state. The Q-value update rule is based on the Bellman equation depicted in Equation (1). The following notation is adopted:

$$Q_{\phi}(x, u) = r + \gamma \max_{u'} Q_{\phi}(x', u') - Q_{\phi}(x, u) \quad (1)$$

Figure 2: Diagrammatic representation of the Bellman equation (BLE)

Figure 2 depicts the foundational principle guiding the decision-making of the reinforcement learning agent, which is derived from the Bellman equation 1.1. This equation encapsulates the core concept of value iteration in RL, where an agent evaluates the expected cumulative reward of taking a specific action u in a given state x , considering both immediate rewards r and the discounted future rewards determined by the optimal action u' in the next state x' . The Bellman framework allows the trained agents to learn adaptive policies aimed at minimizing congestion within the context of traffic coordination in Port Harcourt's critical junctions—specifically Choba, Rumuokoro, and Eleme. As each agent interacts with the environment, the Q-values are iteratively updated based on the observed traffic conditions and the actions taken. The integration of GNNs enables the model to represent each junction as a node, preserving the spatial relationships and directional dependencies inherent in the city's road topology. Consequently, the RL agent does not simply react to localized conditions but develops a coordinated strategy informed by the broader network structure. The Bellman update mechanism reinforces the selection of actions that alleviate immediate congestion and improve long-term flow efficiency across interconnected junctions. This RL approach is vital in dynamically evolving environments, such as urban traffic systems, where real-time data and historical trends must be harmonized to achieve optimal control policies.

Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC)

The codebase was developed using an Agile-inspired SDLC, informed by Eman A. Altameem's study on the impact of agile methodologies, which highlights its flexibility, stakeholder engagement, and high-quality iterative delivery as key enablers for complex projects. (Altameem, 2015). Figure 3 shows a simple block diagram of the behavior of the system. Specifically, the system adopted includes the following:

1. **Requirement Analysis:** Key traffic hotspots were identified using city datasets.
2. **System Design:** Defined agent architecture, environment structure, and graph topology.
3. **Implementation:** Iterative sprints using Python, TensorFlow, and the Google Cloud Platform were implemented, with each sprint delivering testable modules.
4. **Testing and Review:** Sprint-end demos and stakeholder reviews ensured an early feedback, aligning with Agile best practices.
5. **Deployment:** Multi-episode simulations with benchmarked reward stability.

6. **Maintenance and Retrospective:** Periodic retrospectives informed the hyperparameter tuning and architecture refinement.

According to Altameem, agile methods "help develop quality products", boost creativity, and reduce costs through stakeholder engagement and early fault detection. These qualities are essential when developing a dynamic, data-driven MADRL system.

Multiple Agents and Reduction of Bias

DQN agents observe environment states and select actions based on the highest Q-values, which may introduce a positive bias. To address this, a hybrid DQN architecture was utilized, where one network learns from another, reducing the likelihood of overestimation. This is aligned with Kim (2022), who implemented an N-DQN structure to exploit the benefits of parallelized training across multiple agents. Gott et al. (2021) demonstrated the effectiveness of MADRL in achieving city-level objectives, reporting reductions in voltage instabilities of up to 34%. This reinforces the scalability and robustness of the proposed approach.

Figure 3: Block diagram and flow chart of the DQN Graph Neural Networks

Graph layers are integrated into the DQN architecture to model the complex road network of Port Harcourt. Each node in the graph represents a traffic junction, and the edges indicate road connectivity. An adjacency matrix, constructed using TensorFlow's tfgnn and tf.sparse utilities, captures spatial dependencies. TensorFlow Graph Neural Network (TF-GNN) automatically supports efficient probabilistic message passing and optimizes edge-level information flow across nodes." (TensorFlow, 2024).

The advantage of using GNNs is their capacity to learn spatial correlations between traffic intersections, leading to agents' more informed decision-making. The use of dense variational Bayesian layers, which provide probabilistic output distributions, improves generalization and uncertainty estimation. Bayesian neural networks

effectively model epistemic uncertainty, which is the uncertainty in model parameters due to limited data. As explained by Depeweg et al. (2018), epistemic uncertainty is crucial in safety-critical and dynamic domains, where models must express confidence about predictions. Using reparameterization and variational inference techniques, TensorFlow inherently addresses epistemic uncertainty through probabilistic backpropagation. These capabilities are critical in producing reliable predictions under uncertainty, particularly in traffic control tasks where real-time decisions affect public safety. This choice counters the typical problem of overfitting in traffic prediction models, offering better adaptability to dynamic road scenarios.

Custom Environment

Unlike conventional RL training on synthetic environments (e.g., OpenAI Gym), a bespoke environment that directly interacts with real-world traffic data was developed. The environment replicates traffic patterns and congestion levels in Port Harcourt, allowing agents to be trained on contextually relevant episodes. Each episode corresponds to a time slice of urban traffic, and the agent receives rewards based on prediction accuracy and congestion mitigation.

This approach offers the following advantages:

- Eliminating the domain gap between simulation and real-world deployment
- Time-sensitive training (e.g., rush hour vs. off-peak)
- Increases agent interpretability and behavior traceability

Conclusion

The DQN is written in Python, inheriting from TensorFlow, and the training program is run for 100 episodes. It can be accessed using a web interface, as it is hosted on the Google Cloud Platform. In the first episode, substantial difficulty was observed as the agent registered negative rewards. Stability is ensured by introducing clipping and enforcing a fixed length for episodes with an enforced terminal condition by setting the “done” flag to true, reflecting the meaningful task compilation. These improvements improved training consistency, learning rate behavior, and policy convergence.

Figure 4: Trend in episode reward

Figure 4 depicts the cumulative reward trendline behavior over training episodes. In episode 8, the agent develops a policy that allows it to make decisions within 20 steps. Although the cumulative rewards remain notably

negative, around -4×10^8 , which tilts toward the agent's inability to learn positive actions. Even though the smoothness and repeatability of the curve show the agent trying and failing at the task. The reward function, which used a generally negative mean-squared error approach to minimize large error values, which are clipped to avoid explosive values, was modified to use a generally positive approach, which then shows the model can see positive rewards, so it knows what actions to prioritize over others. It is a more compartmentalized approach that adds bonuses based on map error using mean absolute percentage error to modify the final reward, thereby making the model chase after these bonuses by keeping the error within a limit regardless of the size of variables and polarity. The overall growth in the average reward and total rewards per episode after 100 episodes is observed after the modification.

Figure 5: Total and average reward of the agent after 100 episodes of learning behavior across trials

Figure 6: Learning rate consistency across the 10 training trials

Figure 6 presents the learning rate behaviors over the 10 independent training trials. The learning rate remained stable and consistent across all runs, which is crucial for convergence in deep reinforcement learning. The smooth trendline indicates that the training regime, including fixed learning rates and clipping strategies, successfully mitigated the risk of exploding or vanishing gradients, which are common DQN training pitfalls.

Figure 7: Entropy profile of samples

Figure 7 shows the evolution of entropy across samples. The entropy values stabilized around 0.003, implying that the agent has developed a confident yet slightly exploratory policy. A lower entropy generally indicates that the agent has converted to a more deterministic set of actions, which reduces randomness. However, maintaining a non-zero entropy helps prevent premature convergence to suboptimal policies, a critical aspect when operating in environments with non-stationary or partially observable dynamics. The plateau in entropy aligns with the convergence of rewards, further confirming the formation of stable policy.

As discussed previously, the model's performance is compared to the real-life conditions by predicting the outcome at a particular time and then physically going to check the junction's current state.

Figure 8: Dashboard prediction of the Rumuokoro Junction

As shown in Figure 8, the prediction for July 13th, at 5:02 pm, was low traffic congestion. Figure 9 shows pictures of Rumuokoro Junction at 5:02 pm. The results are validated by physically checking the junction condition versus the model performance. Figure 9 shows sparse traffic congestion at Rumuokoro Junction at the given location. Lanes have to be mapped to show the probability of one lane generating more traffic than another, which is a problem captured at Rumuokoro Junction, where the lane that feeds traffic to Rumuokoro Junction has a higher chance of causing traffic congestion.

Figure 9: Validation of the Rumuokoro Junction prediction

Figure 10: Dashboard prediction of the Eliozu Junction

At Eliozu Junction prediction as shown in Figure 10 on July 14 at 7:38 am, the model predicts low traffic at 7:38 through a mobile device. Figure 11 shows the site pictures taken at the junction, which depict sparse road congestion at the given time.

Figure 11: Validation of the Eliozu junction prediction

The prediction given by the model at Choba on July 14 at 1:48 am is shown in Figure 10. However, certain factors are predominant, including the possibility of bad vehicle parking (cited along the road leading away from Choba Junction) and stores encroaching on the road. These factors constitute traffic congestion at Choba, which is not adequately captured in the training dataset. The model is accessed using the Windows Chrome browser.

Figure 12: Dashboard prediction and Choba Junction prediction validation

Elem Junction hosts one of the most intricate road network constructions in Port Harcourt. The prediction given by the model using the command line to query the model is shown in Figure 13. Returns a JSON object along with other parameters. The prediction for Eleme Junction on July 19 at 11:40 am is given as “high,” as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 13: Command line prediction and Choba Junction prediction validation

Although high traffic is not present at Eleme Junction, as shown in Figure 12, if carefully examined, the junctions leading to Eleme experience a noticeable level of traffic congestion, as shown in Figure 14. The congestion buildup along routes that lead in and out of Eleme Junction, but its behavior is not adequately captured with the current dataset due to its complex nature.

Figure 14: Validation of the Eleme prediction along the Aba Road

From the Eleme Junction, going toward Aba Road, a noticeable traffic congestion buildup is observed, as shown in Figure 14. This congestion has a scaling factor created by the roadside sellers.

Figure 15: Validation of the Eleme prediction along East-West Road

From the oil mill to the Eleme junction, traffic congestion can be interpreted as high, with a noticeable standstill of motorists. This can be attributed to the constant encroachment of markets on the road network.

Summary of the observations

Overall, the agent demonstrated clear learning ability following the reward graph, although using a negative approach did not allow the model to learn good behavior. The normalization of error was carried out to reduce the blowing up of errors and prevent the model from learning. The graph layer, which enables the agent to learn dependencies, fails at complex road networks, as seen at the Eleme junction. The problem can be labeled as the lack of a robust dataset. Future researchers are encouraged to build a graph layer to map complex junction networks, such as Eleme.

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